

INNOVATIVE METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH TO YOUNG CHILDREN.

Norbo'tayeva Dilshoda

Termiz State University

4th year student of the Faculty of Foreign Philology,

ABSTRACT: This article describes innovative methods of teaching English to young children. And it is said to enable the implementation of these methods in a new approach. In this article, you can get acquainted with meaningful and interesting methods of teaching English in preschool education and primary classes using modern information technologies and game methods.

Key words: innovative, technology, possibility, approach, method, teaching.

After our country gained independence, great attention has been paid to learning foreign languages in our country. In particular, the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the further improvement of the system of learning foreign languages" adopted on December 10, 2012, and the introduction of foreign languages in the first classes of general education schools from the 2013-2014 school year. the introduction of continuous training is proof of this. Nowadays, foreign language, especially English, is taught not only to students of schools, lyceums, colleges and universities, but also to students of M.T.M. and employees working in various fields. There's a reason for that, of course. Learning the languages of economically, scientifically, and culturally developed countries is the main factor in acquiring the achievements of world science and development. Language learning also depends on age. According to psychologists, children learn language faster and easier than adults. The main reasons for this are the natural tendency of children to learn a language, the fact that they have a strong ability to imitate, and the fact that children have more time than adults. It should be noted that 6-7-year-old children do not understand the meaning of information, but memorize it mechanically. Therefore, it is necessary not to start teaching English to elementary school students with grammatical concepts. Otherwise, from the first step of teaching a foreign language, it is possible to strain the child and extinguish his interest. Therefore, teaching a foreign language to young children is very difficult and responsible. The following methods can be used to teach English to children in a meaningful and interesting way: - through songs and poems, to teach the letters or combinations that are difficult to

explain or remember, and have no meaning. for example, it can be shown that children's learning the English alphabet by singing is more effective than just memorizing.-games related to mental and physical activities;-cartoons; Although children do not understand the words in the cartoon during language learning, they try to understand the words they use through the actions of the cartoon characters. This is an interesting and effective way for children to learn the language. -role play (role play) the teacher should role-play or play it to children while teaching some information, for example, the names of animals or birds. For example: if one student shows howling of a dog and meowing of a cat, another student needs to find out which animal these sounds belong to and say its English name. - environment related to the topic; Children learn the language better if the teacher can create that environment depending on the topic. For example: traveling, birthday, in the kitchen, etc. On the topic of traveling, the teacher will organize a trip, what means of travel can be used (foot, bicycle, automobile, train, boat, airplane), where to travel (Tashkent, Samarkand, Bukhara, England, USA). gives information about its importance. It strengthens the students' vocabulary, language abilities, and develops their worldview.-riddles; Children have a strong interest in finding answers to riddles. Therefore, when the teacher says the riddle in English or Uzbek, he should ask the children to say the answer in English. Then children learn words quickly. practical activities (tasting fruits and other foods, smelling flowers); This sentence can be explained by the thoughts of a practicing psychologist: "The pedagogue who wants something to be firmly fixed in the children's memory should use as many of the child's senses as possible: eyes, ears, sound organs, muscle sensations and, if possible, even if there is, he should try to involve the organs of smell and taste in the process of remembering". For example: when a student tastes an apple, the teacher gives information about its color (red) or green (green), taste (tasty) or sour (), smell () and He should feed the fruits to other students and ask them to give information about that fruit in English. This will also help the child in his further studies. he immediately remembers the moment he ate the fruit, he quickly remembers that it is red-red and green-green. Therefore, the use of such a method ensures that the student will retain information in his memory for a long time. - through gestures, facial expressions; When the teacher says something to the child or gives an order, for example, if the child uses gestures in sentences such as "come here", "open the book", "stand up", "look at the blackboard" will be understandable.-through visual aids, posters, books;-writing on things that are visible and often used in everyday life.

For example: writing on a door, book, table, blackboard, window, etc. Since such things are always visible and often used in practice, the child learns these words involuntarily.

Teaching with updated methods increases children's aspirations. Preschool age is especially convenient for starting to learn a foreign language: children of this age are distinguished by their sensitivity to language phenomena, they are interested in understanding their speech experiences, the "secrets" of language. They easily and firmly remember a small amount of language material and multiply it well. With age, these favorable factors lose their power. There is another reason why an early age is better for learning a foreign language. The younger the child, the smaller the vocabulary in the local language, but at the same time his needs for speech are less: in a small child there are fewer areas of communication than in adults, he does not yet have to solve complex communication problems. This means that when he learns a foreign language, he will not notice such a big difference between the opportunities in his native and foreign languages, and his sense of success will be brighter than that of older children. Teaching children requires a completely different methodological approach than schoolchildren and adults. a very difficult issue that requires If an adult speaks a foreign language, it does not mean that he can teach it to others. When faced with methodologically inefficient lessons, children may long-term hate the foreign language and lose confidence in their abilities. Only experienced professionals should work with preschool children. The methodology of conducting direct educational activities should be built taking into account the age and individual characteristics of the structure of children's language skills and should be directed to their development. Communication in a foreign language should be motivational and focused. It is necessary to create a positive psychological attitude towards a foreign language in a child, and the way to create such a positive motivation is to play. We know that children are curious, so using games, pictures, songs and poems, cartoons is an effective way to teach foreign language to young children. Because the main concept in them is depicted in a picture in the brain. This in turn requires us to describe everything we teach accordingly. The psychology of children studying in preschool and elementary grades is based on the category of enthusiasm and liking. Young children are naturally very interested in bright and beautiful things and pay a lot of attention. Therefore, it is an effective way for teachers and coaches to use more game methods. In our current modern life, foreign language, especially English, is taught not only to students of schools, lyceums, colleges and universities, but also to students

of preschool educational institutions and employees working in various fields. . The reason is that learning the languages of economically, scientifically and culturally developed countries is the main factor in acquiring the achievements of world science and development. According to Professor Wilga M. Rivers of Harvard University, one of the famous representatives of the methodology of teaching foreign languages, to be literate is to read and means to know the writing. Language learning also depends on age. According to scientists and psychologists, children learn language faster and easier than adults. Another method of quality teaching is a special group with deep (up to full immersion) training and a full language environment using video and audio recordings of native speakers. We talked about this method earlier. However, not always and not all parents like such groups to their taste and pocket. If you want to achieve a positive result, follow a few rules. First of all, remember that learning a foreign language cannot be forced. The more you force, the less the baby wants to do something. Perhaps, first of all, it is worth trying interesting online English courses on the Internet to encourage the child to learn the subject, to arouse his interest. An integrated approach is also important. In no case should you focus only on learning grammar. The training plan should be prepared carefully and thoughtfully. Patience is required. The child should know that he has stepped on a difficult path, but the reward for his efforts will be priceless. The presence of motivation is the key to success in learning any subject.

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